

DiSSCo Transition Project

**Report on standards adoption including
workshops, current state of
geo-collections data mobilisation and
documentation for DiSSCo services**

Work Package 4 - Deliverable 4.2

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Executive Summary

This report (DTP D4.2) presents an overview of the adoption of data standards work within the DiSSCo Transition Project, focusing on current efforts to mobilise collections data and document DiSSCo services. It describes two key workshops designed to promote community engagement and technical implementation of emerging standards. The first workshop introduced the newly ratified Latimer Core (LtC) standard for collection descriptions, using Airtable templates and real-world examples to demonstrate its utility. The second workshop focused on machine-actionable Data Management Plans (maDMPs) and taxon hypothesis standards, showcasing implementations on the PlutoF platform and UNITE data. The report also highlights the functional documentation and infrastructure support provided to enable DiSSCo service integration. Key recommendations emphasise the need for expanded training, broader stakeholder engagement, and development of practical, real-world examples to enhance standards adoption.

Keywords: Biodiversity informatics, Data standards, Latimer Core, Machine-actionable Data Management Plans (maDMPs), Taxon Concept Schema (TCS), Research infrastructure, Geo-collections, DiSSCo (Distributed System of Scientific Collections), Digital specimen, FAIR data principles, Workshops

List of abbreviations

BiCIKL - Biodiversity Community Integrated Knowledge Library

CETAF - Consortium of European Taxonomic Facilities

COGs - Collection Object Groups

CSV - Comma-Separated Values

DiSSCo - Distributed System of Scientific Collections

DiSSCo UK - Distributed System of Scientific Collections UK (national node and programme for UK collections digitisation)

DiSSCo Flanders - Distributed System of Scientific Collections Belgium (national node and programme for Belgian collections digitisation)

DMP - Data Management Plan

GBIF - Global Biodiversity Information Facility

GRSciColl - Global Registry of Scientific Collections

JSON - JavaScript Object Notation,

maDMPs - machine-actionable Data Management Plans

MOTs - Multiple Object Types

LtC - Latimer Core

TCS - Taxon Concept Schema

TDWG - Biodiversity Information Standards, formerly Taxonomic Databases Working Group

WP4 - Workpackage 4 (WP4) "International Collaboration on (data) Standards"

1. Workshop Delivery in DTP

The first workshop, held at the SPNHC-TDWG 2024 conference in Okinawa, introduced the Latimer Core (LtC) data standard to 15–20 participants. Using Airtable for demonstrations, the session guided participants through structured exercises and real-world templates, notably a digitisation planning example from NHM London. The workshop revealed a strong interest in more contextual examples, more time for foundational data concepts, and the need for role-specific sessions. Despite time constraints, the training was well-received, and all materials were made freely available under an open license.

The second workshop, held in Tartu, Estonia, in January 2025, introduced 40–50 participants to machine-actionable Data Management Plans (maDMPs) and updates to the Taxon Concept Schema (TCS). Day 1 focused on maDMP implementation via the PlutoF platform, while Day 2 explored taxon hypotheses through expert presentations and discussion. While technical demonstrations were successfully delivered, limited hands-on engagement and feedback highlighted the need for more interactive and structured training materials. The workshop reinforced the importance of continued standards development and collaboration through the TDWG community.

1.1 Workshop 1

1.1.1 Summary / Introduction

In the DiSSCo Transition project, Workpackage 4 (WP4) “International Collaboration on (data) Standards” has the objective to support continued development and adoption of new community standards. As part of our WP4 work, we prepared and ran the first user workshop for the newly ratified Latimer Core (LtC) data standard. Preparation included: selecting a freely available system that we could implement LtC in (Airtable); creating generic LtC templates that would be suitable for different uses; creating reference content based on a real use case (collections audit prior to specimen-level digitisation) at the NHM; creating workshop content including a presentation and orientation/exercises for participants.

Preparation was done in collaboration with the TDWG Collections Descriptions (CD) Task Group, a community group which developed the LtC data standard.

We delivered the workshop to 15-20 participants in a hybrid workshop at the SPNHC-TDWG 2024 Conference in Okinawa, Japan on September 4th, 2024.

All workshop material was made available in Zenodo under a permissive CC-BY 4.0 license (Livermore, L., Woodburn, M., & Norton, B. (2024)). The workshop material was designed to be re-usable/customisable for future workshops.

1.1.2 Workshop Objectives

The workshop had the following five objectives for participants:

1. Understand how Latimer Core (Lc) can be used and how you might use it
2. Become familiar with the Latimer Core data structure
3. Create your own Latimer Core dataset that you can continue to edit after the workshop
4. Give feedback on how we can support you implement new standards for your work
5. Understand how you can participate in standards development

1.1.3 Workshop Preparation

Content preparation consisted of four parts:

1. Technical

- a. Platform - Latimer Core is a complex hierarchical standard and requires database functionality to properly implement and use. We chose to run the training using Airtable, a cloud-based spreadsheet-database hybrid. This allowed us to create prototypes and run training with free accounts without complex hosting or permission management.
- b. Airtable Bases - Latimer Core was designed to cover a range of use cases, with the concept that users/implementers are likely to use a subset of its functionality depending on purpose. We created two Airtable Bases – essentially templates – for the training. One base is effectively an empty template without data that represents the complete scope of Latimer Core. It was intended to act as a basis for users to test out different use cases. The second base is a real-world template complete with data, used for planning and tracking the digitisation of NHM London’s British and Irish Coleoptera dry, pinned insect collection.
2. **Presentation (PowerPoint)** – the presentation was based on a previous overview of the Latimer Core standard given to the 2024 NatSCA Conference (Livermore and Woodburn, 2024) but with additional slides for orientation and task-based exercises to supplement the documentation.
3. **Documentation (PDF)** – orientation information for users on the Latimer Core standard with links to Airtable Bases and a set of structured tasks to help users become familiar with the Latimer Core standard and add their own data.
4. **Survey** – A user feedback survey built in Google Forms.
5. **Closed testing and feedback** – We asked members of the TDWG Collections Descriptions (CD) Task Group to give feedback on the presentation and documentation. Shelly James did complete testing of our test version of documentation for which we are very grateful!

1.1.4 Workshop Structure / Agenda

The workshop was around 90 minutes long and included the following sections:

- Introduction ~ 5 minutes
 - Objectives & outcomes
 - Standards work in DiSSCo Transition
- Overview of Latimer Core ~15 minutes

- Applications of Latimer Core ~15 minutes
- Orientation and exercises ~45 minutes
- Wrap-up ~10 minutes
 - Discussion & feedback
 - Resources and acknowledgements

1.1.5 Workshop Participants

The workshop had around 15-20 participants from three continents (Europe, North America, Asia). There was a sign-up sheet but there were additional attendees on the day.

Known/registered participants were a mix of collections staff (e.g., curators/collection managers), technical staff (e.g., working for GBIF on GRSciColl), and commercial technology/service suppliers.

1.1.6 Workshop Delivery

The workshop was delivered as a hybrid workshop run via Zoom at the Okinawa Convention Centre, Japan.

The workshop started with a presentation, then a mix of screen sharing and narrative to guide participants through Latimer and our Airtable implementation.

1.1.7 Outcomes, Results, Challenges and Lessons Learned

We successfully delivered the course and received good verbal feedback but got no structured survey feedback from participants.

Prior to delivering the course we had already noted that 90 minutes would be tight for delivering both practical overview of the standard and hands-on training in applying it to data. Latimer Core is a complex and structured data standard and would benefit from a slower introduction into the concepts and usage. Time should be factored in to help participants to understand the basic concepts of relational data models as used by LtC, as many in the community are more accustomed to working with relatively flat data in spreadsheet and CSV format. Similarly, if using a structured software tool like Airtable to demonstrate LtC, there should be time allowances to help participants to familiarise themselves with the software before progressing to the LtC-specific parts of the training.

Recommendation 1) For subsequent training, we would recommend at least half a day or ~3 hours of training, which includes familiarisation with structured data concepts and the training tool.

Latimer Core is a new standard, and so far has limited examples of real world applications. While we provided one real example (a digitisation audit use case at NHM London), we recognise that it would be easier for people to understand the potential applications of LtC if they had more reference examples and templates that align with their own collection description use cases. Some examples raised in the workshop included: recent

acquisitions (e.g., collection bequeathments/purchases, field work/expeditions), linking collections with associated archival materials and publications, creating institutional collections profiles for national/transnational programmes (e.g., DiSSCo EU, DiSSCo Flanders and DiSSCo UK).

Recommendation 2) Develop more demonstration templates, with narratives that put them in the context of real-world use cases.

Following on from the previous recommendation, workshop participants requested focused sessions on specific examples that would be relevant to their work.

Recommendation 3) Run specific sessions focused on thematically related sets of use cases.

The workshop included participants with a range of levels of technical proficiency, from relatively basic to highly skilled in systems and data. This often makes it difficult to tailor the training content and pace so that it is most effective for all of the participants. As a new standard, there is also a fairly small number of people who have enough of a grounding in the standard to be able to deliver training, and the demand is likely to outstrip the supply at the present time.

Recommendation 4) Run sessions specific to different stakeholder groups, including train-the-trainer sessions to widen the pool of community resources for LtC training.

The Airtable software is well suited to demonstrating working with structured LtC data, due to the ease of creating relational data tables that closely mirror the structure of the LtC data model and configuring forms on top of the data that demonstrate how it might be managed through a user interface. Workshop participants were provided with the facility to take copies of the demo databases to explore in their own Airtable workspaces in their own time. However, Airtable is a commercial, hosted-only product, and the free tier of licensing has restrictions that make it difficult to scale up to any production application without incurring costs. Other similar no-code options (with differing degrees of maturity and richness of functionality) are available that offer open-source self-hosting options, such as BaseRow, NocoDB and Grist. These may offer alternative approaches to LtC prototyping and demonstration that also offer a clearer path to scaling up use to production levels.

Recommendation 5) Explore similar technologies to Airtable that have fewer restrictions on use without incurring costs.

1.1.8 Future Work / Next Steps

The next steps for the Latimer Core standard itself, and the TDWG Maintenance Group that supports it, are primarily focused on working with stakeholders towards practical applications of the standard. The ability (through the approaches introduced in this workshop) to be able to demonstrate what LtC might look like in a data schema, and how

it might look in a corresponding user interface, are important steps in that direction. They should provide some solid ground for focusing conversations with stakeholders from both a technical and an operational perspective. This is also likely to support continued work in Work Package 4 on developing LtC schemas, with associated JSON schemas, that align with DiSSCo EU service requirements and providing a standards-based route to interoperability with other collections data aggregators like national DiSSCo nodes, GRSciColl and the CETAF Registry of Collections.

In terms of next steps for training and developing the demonstration material and platform, we will take the feedback and learnings from the workshop to develop a set of actions to further refine the approach, with reference to the recommendations in the previous section. The route to sustainability is likely to primarily lie with the TDWG Collection Descriptions Interest Group, pending discussions on handover of materials and training/support plans under the TDWG umbrella for the future.

1.2 Workshop 2

1.2.1 Summary / Introduction

In the DiSSCo Transition project, Work Package 4 (WP4), titled “International Collaboration on (data) Standards” aims to facilitate ongoing development and adoption of new community standards. As part of our WP4 work, we prepared and delivered the second technical workshop on the machine-actionable DiSSCo Data Management Plan (DMP) and standards for taxon hypotheses. The workshop provided an overview of: (1) machine-actionability in DMPs, followed by a demonstration of machine-actionable DMP (maDMP) implementation on the PlutoF platform, and (2) the Taxon Concept Schema (TCS)¹ and the significant modifications introduced by the TCS 2 Task Group (Klazenga and Liljeblad, 2024). We explored how these updates enable the schema to accommodate and build practical applications on DNA-based taxon hypotheses (TH), especially those that lack formally described taxon names (Kõljalg et al., 2020). Additionally, Taxonomic Data Objects (Upham and Poelen 2024) – digital, machine-actionable taxonomic references – and their integration within an open, infrastructure-focused framework (Islam et al., 2024) were addressed in the context of this topic.

The preparation involved:

- Creating a machine-actionable DMP (maDMP) for the DiSSCo infrastructure on PlutoF platform, incorporating example datasets and services to demonstrate its machine-actionability.
- Developing an example implementation of the Taxon Concept Standard (TCS) applied to UNITE Taxon Hypotheses – a unified system for DNA-based fungal species linked to classification.
- Designing workshop content, including presentations by the workshop authors and invited speakers, along with discussion points for participants.

¹ <https://www.tdwg.org/standards/tcs>

We delivered the workshop to 40-50 participants in a hybrid workshop in Tartu, Estonia, on January 21-22, 2025.

All workshop materials, including PowerPoint slides, and Zoom recordings, were made available on the DiSSCo homepage².

1.2.2 Workshop Objectives

The workshop had the following five objectives for participants:

1. Provide an overview of machine-actionability in DMPs.
2. Present an overview of the DiSSCo Transition Project's Task 3.3 activities and facilitate a review and discussion of the current DMP draft for the DiSSCo infrastructure.
3. Conduct a hands-on session to demonstrate the creation of maDMPs and provide an overview of the test implementation of DiSSCo's maDMP on the PlutoF platform.
4. Introduce the Taxon Concept Standard (TCS) and its latest updates.
5. Explore how Taxon and Species Hypotheses can be managed as FAIR data.

1.2.3 Workshop Preparation

Content preparation consisted of two parts:

1. Technical
 - a. Developing a test machine-actionable DMP for the DiSSCo architecture on the PlutoF platform³. We identified datasets and services produced by the DiSSCo project to showcase the machine-actionable functionality of the DMP. This included searching and browsing project-related datasets in the DiSSCo Knowledgebase⁴ and Zenodo⁵.
 - b. Developing an example implementation of the TCS applied to UNITE Taxon Hypotheses⁶. During this process, we identified several issues with the current TCS standard that require further discussion and development.
2. Presentations (PowerPoint) – several presentations and hands-on session tutorial covering maDMPs and standards for taxon hypotheses.

1.2.4 Workshop Structure / Agenda

The workshop was divided into two parts, held on separate days. Day 1: "DiSSCo DMP for machine-actionability" (approximately 80 minutes) included the following sections:

- Introduction
- Overview of machine-actionability in Data Management Plans
- Overview of DiSSCo Transition Project's Task 3.3 and Deliverable 3.3 activities
- Review and discussion of the current DMP draft for the DiSSCo

² <https://www.dissco.eu/dissco-transition-dmp-standards-taxon-hypotheses>

³ <https://plutof.ut.ee>

⁴ <https://know.dissco.eu>

⁵ <https://zenodo.org>

⁶ https://github.com/kessya/TCS_UNITE_SH

Infrastructure

- Hands-on Session: Creating maDMPs in PlutoF
- Test implementation of DiSSCo's maDMP on the PlutoF platform
- Discussion and feedback

Day 2: "Standards for Taxon Hypotheses" (approximately 135 minutes) included the following sections:

- Introduction
- Presentation by Niels Klazenga – *"The Taxon Concept Standard (TCS)"*
- Presentation by Urmas Kõljalg – *"UNITE standard of the Taxon Hypotheses"*
- Presentation by Sharif Islam – *"Taxon and Species Hypotheses as FAIR Data: BINs, OTUs, ASVs, TCS, and Beyond into the Biodiversity Data Ecosystem"*
- Coffee break
- Presentation by Tobias G. Frøslev – *"GBIF Backbone Taxonomy & Catalogue of Life"*
- Open discussion

1.2.5 Workshop Participants

The workshop had 67 registrants, primarily from Europe, with some participants from Australia and the United States. Some registrants attended only the first or second day. During the Zoom sessions, we observed approximately 35-40 participants on both days.

Registered participants were a mix of collections staff (e.g., curators/collection managers), technical staff (e.g., database and system developers), and DiSSCo National Nodes representatives.

1.2.6 Workshop Delivery

The workshop was delivered as a hybrid workshop run via Zoom at the University of Tartu, Estonia.

The workshop began with a presentation on the machine-actionability of DMPs, followed by a hands-on session and a demonstration of the DMP module on the PlutoF platform, led by Kessy Abarenkov. On the second day, invited speakers delivered a series of presentations on Taxon Concepts and Taxon Hypotheses Standards, followed by an open discussion led by Urmas Kõljalg.

1.2.7 Outcomes, Results, Challenges and Lessons Learned

We successfully delivered the workshop and received good verbal feedback; however, we did not collect structured survey feedback from participants.

Since the topic of Day 1 was new to many participants, the workshop primarily functioned as a presentation and demonstration of the test implementation rather than the planned hands-on and discussion session, resulting in shorter duration than expected.

Recommendation 1: For future training sessions, we recommend putting more effort into designing discussion points and preparing exercise sheets for participants to work through during the hands-on session.

The second day of the workshop, which featured four presentations, was followed by a very interesting and useful discussion that also involved participants who were not presenters. Based on this, we recommend inviting multiple presenters who can provide more depth on the topic covered in the workshop.

Recommendation 2: For future training sessions, we recommend inviting additional presenters to introduce the workshop topics in greater depth.

1.2.8 Future Work / Next Steps

We hope that the workshop will generate suggestions and feedback on the machine-actionable DMP for the DiSSCo infrastructure, including its draft document and deliverable (D3.3). We will continue working on implementing functionality and enhancing the user interface for the machine-actionability of DMPs in PlutoF, as well as regularly updating the list of datasets and services that form part of the DiSSCo's maDMP to demonstrate its applicability and usefulness for managing data in research projects. Additionally, we will monitor the progress of the [OSTrails project](#), which is developing the Plan-Track-Assess framework – a high-level, tool-independent framework that guides researchers, research managers, and funders in planning, tracking, and assessing the management of Digital Objects in their DMPs, in alignment with the FAIR principles – to stay informed about new developments and tools in this field.

We will continue developing and improving standards for Taxon Hypotheses by forwarding the knowledge and discussion outputs from the workshop to the Taxon Concept Schema 2 Task Group (Klazenga and Liljeblad, 2024). We will also continue building an implementation of the TCS using UNITE Taxon and Species Hypotheses as a test case.

2. Geo-collections data mobilisation

GeoCASE has been a key platform for mobilising Earth science specimen data across institutions. However, its adoption and effectiveness have been limited by several challenges. A major barrier is the technical and logistical burden placed on institutions, particularly the requirement to install and manage BioCASE software, which necessitates IT support that many providers lack. As a result, participation from data-holding institutions remains low. Additionally, inconsistent application of data standards creates interoperability issues, while poor metadata quality—such as missing identifiers and incomplete records—limits the discoverability and usability of the data.

A user survey conducted in 2022, involving 21 participants, identified the top priorities for improving the GeoCASE platform. These include aligning with global data standards such as ABCD-EFG, Darwin Core, and MIDS; improving metadata quality to enhance discoverability and research usability; and expanding data enrichment to provide richer

contextual information. Lower-ranked priorities, such as visualisation tools and external dataset linking, reflect a clear consensus that improving core data quality is the foundational step before building out more advanced features.

In response to these needs, CETAF will work closely with DiSSCo to connect GeoCASE to the DiSSCo API. This integration will enable automated harvesting and validation of specimen data from institutional repositories, significantly reducing dependence on BioCASE for DiSSCo member institutions. Moreover, it will improve alignment with broader European digital infrastructure efforts, streamlining participation in pan-European data networks.

To support institutions outside DiSSCo, CETAF also plans to host a centralised BioCASE installation on its own servers. This approach eliminates the need for individual institutions to install and maintain their own instances of the software, thereby reducing technical barriers and simplifying the data-sharing workflow for a wider group of contributors.

In addition, external initiatives contributing to the advancement of geological data management is GeoSpecify ([Extending Specify 7 for Geoscience Collections](#)). Developed through a European collaboration involving US, Swiss and EU institutions, GeoSpecify extends the open-source Specify 7 collections management system to meet the specialised needs of geological collections (Miller & Fitzsimmons, 2024). It addresses the limitations of traditional biological data models by introducing features specific to geological specimens such as rocks, minerals, fossils, and meteorites.

Key features include support for Multiple Object Types (MOTs) tailored to different specimen categories, Collection Object Groups (COGs) to link related specimens, expanded stratigraphic fields (e.g., chronostratigraphy, lithostratigraphy, biostratigraphy), fields for recording absolute numerical ages, and flexible classification tools supporting multiple geological naming systems. GeoSpecify thereby has the potential for facilitating future data provision to platforms like GeoCASE.

3. Functional documentation for DiSSCo services

For DiSSCo services, to support implementing integration with the core infrastructure, a set of functional documentation was provided. Parts of these already were created in previous projects such as BiCIKL, which were complemented with additional documentation in DTP. An overview:

- [BiCIKL D7.1](#) describes the PID infrastructure
- [BiCIKL D7.4](#) describes the Digital Object repository and core infrastructure components
- DTP D3.1 describes the core infrastructure MVP
- DTP MS17 guides DiSSCo services how to integrate with DiSSCo's federated AAI infrastructure services
- DTP D3.3 describes the DiSSCo Data Management Plan
- <https://terms.dissco.tech> describes the openDS data models

- <https://schemas.dissco.tech> includes the JSON schemas for the FDO types and profiles
- a [Swagger endpoint](#) describes the APIs
- the [developers wiki](#) describes the architecture and development methods
- the [MAS developers documentation site](#) contains documentation for MAS developers
- the <https://DiSSCo.tech> blog contains additional background information about for example what a digital specimen is.

4. References

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